

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Using Science, Technology, and Innovation (Sti); in Achieving Sustainable Development in Developing Countries (Dcs)

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Abstract

University-industry relations need to be strengthened; several institutions have technology transfer offices that assist in the formation of spin-off companies. On inventions and technologies, different commercialization routes, the functions of technology transfer offices, and diverse organizational structures will be examined. By showing current innovation and technology, this paper contributes to attaining sustainable development for developed nations by academic and agricultural industry report, development, and commercialization operations. This research aims to analyses and completely examine the scientific and technical literacy approaches for sustainable development in industrialized nations. The evident necessity of sustainable development on supporting scientific and technical advancement in the world's "developed," "developing," and "under-developed" countries is obvious. In this research, we look at how most countries maintain scientific and technical progress. The study also looked at the ideas that underpin the implementation of scientific and technical literacy, with a focus on sustainable development. As a result, proposals on how the Federal government or other agencies may promote sustainable in terms of science, technology, including innovation were made.

Keywords: Science; Technology; Innovation and Sustainable development

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1.Introduction

Another vexing conundrum despite the continuous technological revolution, the majority of the world's population continues to live in abject poverty, with insufficient food, shelter, and electricity, and is afflicted by diseases that might be readily treated if clean water and basic pharmaceuticals were made available. Fortunately, a big number of erstwhile "developing" nations are now on the verge of development, thanks to technical transfer and breakthroughs that have benefitted and continue to benefit substantial segments of their people. Countries like China, India, Korea, Taiwan, Singapore, and, to a degree, Brazil, have pursued their own technical paths. However, the uses of technology remain a pipe dream for large areas of Africa, Asia, but also Latin America, despite the fact that new technologies such as photovoltaics, cellular phones, and indeed the Internet might help them "leap-frog" into the twenty-first century's technological development (Vergragt, 2006). "Development is frequently connected with diverse countries' scientific and technical breakthroughs. The so-called 'developing' nations of Africa may achieve progress, but the primary

challenge is maintaining that development." (Ojimba, 2003).

The persistent contradictions between better lives for the wealthy few created and supported by technology to increase environmental degradation and deprivation for the large majority necessitate a deeper exploration but also understanding of the nature of technology but also its partnership to society, particularly in the context of developing a sustainable, innovation, and creative society (Vergragt, 2006). In the context of efforts to accelerate a massive transition to a more sustainable global society, which will entail significant shifts in culture, beliefs, consumption patterns, governance, industry, and institutions (Raskin et al., 2002), the topic of technology's involvement becomes much more serious.

Technology has been at the forefront of development for centuries transitioning between different stages, passing through industrial ages to our now current technological age. The continuous innovation of technology is what led to the bringing of new products, processes and services enhancing good life to all citizens both rich and poor (Vergragt, 2006). Most of the products used in modern life are products of